

Research Article

The Relationship between Emotional intelligence and quality of life

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ABSTRACT

Research has consistently shown a strong link between emotional intelligence (EI) and quality of life (QoL). Emotional intelligence contributes significantly to various aspects of an individual's well-being, influencing both psychological and social dimensions of quality of life. 80 respondents were examined, 40 women (50%) and 40 men (50%), aged 18 to 65 years. All live in Skopje (100%). In terms of ethnicity, all respondents are Macedonian (100%). In terms of employment and education, all respondents are employed and have faculty degree (100%). Emotional Competence Questionnaire (UEK-45) is used for assessing emotional intelligence. Quality of life is assessed with WHOQOL-BREF. The positive correlation between emotional intelligence and quality of life is found in the actual research. High emotional intelligence facilitates better psychological well-being, physical health, social relationships, and success in personal and professional domains. These factors collectively contribute to a higher quality of life.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, quality of life**Introduction**

Emotional intelligence (EI) is defined as the ability to perceive, understand, manage, and regulate emotions in oneself and others, concept popularized by Daniel Goleman, who identified five key components: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills [1]. The concept of emotional intelligence has roots in earlier theories of social intelligence proposed by E.L. Thorndike in 1920 and Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences in the 1980s. Peter Salovey and John D. Mayer initially coined the term "emotional intelligence" in 1990, defining it as a form of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' emotions, discriminate among them, and use this information to guide one's thinking and actions [2]. High emotional intelligence is associated with better mental health, job performance, leadership skills, and relationships. It contributes to effective communication, conflict resolution, and the ability to navigate social complexities. Individuals with high EI are often more successful in both personal and professional realms because they can manage stress, connect with others, and make informed, empathetic decisions [3-5]. By understanding and developing emotional intelligence, individuals can enhance their interpersonal skills and overall well-being, making it a crucial aspect of personal and professional development.

Quality of life (QoL) is a broad multidimensional concept that encompasses an individual's physical health, psychological state, level of independence, social relationships, personal beliefs, and their relationship to salient features of the environment. It is often used to evaluate the general well-being of individuals and societies [6-9].

Research has consistently shown a strong link between emotional intelligence (EI) and quality of life (QoL). Emotional intelligence contributes significantly to various aspects of an individual's well-being, influencing both psychological and social dimensions of quality of life. Studies indicate that individuals with high EI tend to have better psychological well-being. They are better at managing stress, experiencing fewer symptoms of anxiety and depression, and demonstrating higher levels of life satisfaction [10]. High emotional intelligence is associated with better physical health outcomes. People with higher EI tend to engage in healthier behaviors, manage stress more effectively, and have better immune function [11]. Emotional intelligence enhances social interactions and relationships. Individuals with high EI have better social skills, more supportive social networks, and are more successful in both personal and professional relationships [12]. Research demonstrates that emotional intelligence contributes to academic performance and workplace success. High EI is linked to better academic achievement, leadership qualities, job performance, and job satisfaction [13]. QoL research often focuses on individuals with chronic illnesses, examining how various treatments and interventions affect their well-being. Emotional intelligence plays a role in how patients manage their conditions and maintain a good quality of life [14].

Method

80 respondents were examined, 40 women (50%) and 40 men (50%), aged 18 to 65 years. All live in Skopje (100%). In terms of ethnicity, all respondents are Macedonian (100%). In terms of employment and education, all respondents are employed and have faculty degree (100%). Emotional Competence Questionnaire (UEK-45) is used for assessing emotional intelligence. UEK-45 is an abbreviated version of the UEK-136

Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire, built on the model of the author Takšić, since 1998. The questionnaire contains 45 items classified into three subscales: the ability to perceive and understand emotions (reliability of the scale from $\alpha = .82$ to $\alpha = .88$), the ability to express and name emotions (reliability of the scale from $\alpha = .78$ to $\alpha = .81$) and the ability to control emotions (reliability scale from $\alpha = .68$ to $\alpha = .72$).

Quality of life is assessed with WHOQOL-BREF: A shorter version of the WHOQOL-100, this instrument assesses four domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment. The WHOQOL-BREF had good internal consistency as Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the overall scale was 0.91.

The results are processed in SPSS-26.

Table:1 Emotional intelligence and quality of life

Quality of Life	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Physical	60.5	21.2
Emotional Intelligence	191.16	17.88
Psychosocial	59.8	21.5

Table: 2 Correlation between emotional intelligence and quality of life

Variable	Correlation Coefficient
Quality of Life & EI	.328** / .336**
Significance Level	.001

Discussion

QoL studies frequently address mental health issues, exploring the impact of mental health conditions on life quality and how EI can mitigate negative effects [15]. Research shows that socioeconomic status significantly affects quality of life. Emotional intelligence can buffer the negative impact of low socioeconomic status on quality of life by enhancing coping strategies and resilience [16]. The interrelationship between emotional intelligence and quality of life is well-supported by extensive research. Higher levels of EI contribute to better psychological well-being, improved physical health, stronger social relationships, and greater success in academic and professional settings, all of which enhance overall quality of life. Understanding and developing EI can be a significant step toward improving life satisfaction and well-being [17-22].

This research also confirms a positive connection between emotional intelligence and quality of life. Individuals with higher emotional intelligence tend to report better overall well-being, enhanced mental and physical health, stronger social relationships, and greater life satisfaction. Emotional intelligence contributes significantly to mental health and psychological well-being. High EI individuals are better at managing their emotions, which helps reduce stress, anxiety, and depression. They are also more likely to experience positive emotions and higher life satisfaction. People with high EI are better at recognizing and managing stress, leading to better physical health outcomes. They are more likely to engage in healthy behaviors and have better immune responses, contributing to an overall higher quality of life. Emotional intelligence enhances social interactions by improving empathy, communication, and conflict resolution skills. Individuals with high EI have more supportive and satisfying relationships, which are crucial components of a high quality of life. High EI is linked to better performance in academic and professional settings. This success contributes to overall life satisfaction and well-being, as these areas are significant aspects of an individual's quality of life. Emotional intelligence helps individuals cope with stress by enabling them to perceive, understand, and manage their emotions effectively. This leads to lower lev-

els of stress and its associated negative impacts on quality of life. High EI individuals are better at forming and maintaining positive relationships, which are essential for social support and overall well-being. Quality relationships are a key determinant of life satisfaction. Emotional intelligence includes the ability to regulate one's emotions and maintain motivation. This self-regulation leads to better goal achievement and personal fulfillment, both of which enhance quality of life.

Conclusion

The positive correlation between emotional intelligence and quality of life is well-documented in research, and confirmed in the actual research. High emotional intelligence facilitates better psychological well-being, physical health, social relationships, and success in personal and professional domains. These factors collectively contribute to a higher quality of life.

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